

Report on the different trainings
Deliverable D6.2

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Lead authors:

Sophie Valcke, CERFACS

Other contributing authors:

Julian Kunkel, GWDG

Carlos Osuna, MeteoSwiss

William Barton Sawyer, CSCS

Donatello Elia, CMCC

Alberto Madonna, CSCS

Project internal reviewer:

Joachim Biercamp, DKRZ

Contact details:

Project Office: esiwace@dkrz.de

Visit us on: <https://www.esiwace.eu>

Access our documents in Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>

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1 Abstract /publishable summary

ESiWACE2 WP6 offered trainings on pre-exascale HPC software engineering, methods and tools applied to the domain of weather and climate modelling: I/O, DSL, C++, code coupling, data analytics and containerisation. Resulting material, including presentations and hands-on, was presented at two summer schools organised in August 2020 and 2021. For all trainings, online digital media was also created as Open Educational Resources (OER) material. Originally, online and face-to-face sessions at the partner institutions were planned but all trainings were finally organised online due to the covid-19 pandemic.

2 Conclusion & Results

Different trainings on pre-exascale HPC methods and tools applied to the domain of weather and climate modelling were set up by ESiWACE2, offered through online sessions and during the two ESiWACE Summer Schools.

A Domain Specific Language online training took place on November 23-27, 2020 with 91 people registered. A course on C++ programming was held on October 11-13, 2021, gathering virtually 35 persons. A Short Private Online Course (SPOC) on Code coupling with OASIS3-MCT was set up and in total three sessions took place, one in 2020, 2021 and 2022, respectively, with 32 participants in total. For Visualisation and High Performance Data Analytics, one online training per year was organised in 2020 and 2021, with about 150 participants registered in total, and a third training is planned for September 2022. Lectures and hands-on sessions on Input/Output and Middleware and on Containerisation were delivered as part of the ESiWACE Summer School in August 2020 and 2021, for which 287 participants were registered in total.

All these trainings were well-received and they result in a larger number of scientists and engineers with higher qualifications in HPC for climate and weather applications. Similar training activities should be continued in the third phase of ESiWACE, if funded.

3 Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of the following macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in Section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable
(1) Enable leading European weather and climate models to leverage the available performance of pre-exascale systems with regard to both compute and data capacity in 2021.	X
(2) Prepare the weather and climate community to be able to make use of exascale systems when they become available.	X

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable
Boost European climate and weather models to operate in world-leading quality on existing supercomputing and future pre-exascale platforms	
Establish new technologies for weather and climate modelling	
Enhance HPC capacity of the weather and climate community	X
Improve the toolchain to manage data from climate and weather simulations at scale	
Strengthen the interaction with the European HPC ecosystem	X
Foster co-design between model developers, HPC manufacturers and HPC centres	

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

WP6 has offered diverse training programmes on the topics of pre-exascale HPC software engineering, methods and tools for engineers and scientists in the domain of weather and climate modelling. Trainings were offered in different HPC areas of ESiWACE2 expertise:

- Input/Output and Middleware -see Section 4.1
- Domain Specific Language -see Section 4.2
- C++ programming -see Section 4.3
- Code coupling with OASIS3-MCT -see Section 4.4
- Visualisation and High Performance Data Analytics -see Section 4.5
- Containerisation -see Section 4.6.

Two summer schools, with presentations and hands-on sessions on all these training topics, were organised in August 2020 and 2021 (see Section 4.7). Figure 1 presents a timeline of the different training sessions offered by ESiWACE2.

This deliverable presents the training material and sessions that were organised by ESiWACE2. One can also consult deliverable D6.1 “Report on summer school and its material” (https://zenodo.org/record/5795447#.Yma_my8RpN0) for more detail on the summer schools, and deliverable D6.4 “Training OER material made available under a permissive CC-by licence” (https://zenodo.org/record/5795411#.Yma_Py8RpN0) for a precise description of the Open Educational Resources (OER) material produced based on these trainings.

4.1 Input/Output and Middleware

The training on “Input/Output and Middleware” has consisted of a 90-minute lecture and a 60-minute hands-on part included in each of the two summer schools. For more detail on the participation to the schools, the reader is referred to Section 4.7 and to deliverable D6.1 mentioned above.

Climate and weather research is typically data-intensive and applications must utilise input/output efficiently. Often, users struggle to assess observed performance leading to unsuccessful attempts to tune the application and optimise performance in the wrong layer of the stack. The content of this training on I/O and Middleware was two-fold: Firstly, storage layers focusing on the NetCDF middleware were discussed, and a performance model that aids users to identify inefficient I/O was provided. Secondly, the NetCDF Climate and Forecast (CF) convention, which is often used as a standard to exchange data, was discussed. More specifically, the lecture consisted of:

Figure 1: Training sessions offered during the ESiWACE2 period. Containerisation and Input/Output and Middleware do not specifically appear but are included, like the other training material, in the two summer schools.

- Discussion on the challenges for data-driven research
- Description of the role of middleware and file formats
- Identification of typical I/O performance issues and their causes
- Application of performance models to assess and optimise the application I/O performance
- Design of a data model for NetCDF/CF
- Implementation of an application that utilises parallel I/O to store and analyse data
- Description of ongoing research activities in high performance storage

The hands-on facilitated exploring NetCDF files and utilities. The objectives were to execute programs in C that read and write NetCDF files in a metadata-aware manner, to analyse, manipulate and visualise NetCDF data.

4.2 Domain Specific Language - DSL

This online training took place on November 23-27, 2020, with a total of 91 registered attendees and between 35 and 60 people attending on each of the training days. A survey conducted afterwards yielded 26 responses and revealed that four females, 17 males and five other individuals preferring not to disclose their gender identity had attended the training. The participants were in majority from the academic sector and from many different countries worldwide : 18 Germany, 17 U.K., 12 India, 7 Switzerland, 7 Nigeria, 6 U.S., 4 France, 3 Italy, 3 Turkey, 2 Netherlands, 2 Romania, 2 Spain, 1 Belgium, 1 Brazil, 1 Pakistan, 1 Iran, 1 Argentina, 1 South Africa, 1 Australia.

The training provided insights into the DSLs considered in Earth System Modelling, i.e. the Dusk and Dawn toolchain as well as PsyClone, and demonstrated how to apply them to weather and climate models.

The dusk and dawn lectures contained:

- Short introduction to important concepts in weather models and computational patterns in Finite Volume methods
- In-depth explanation of the dusk frontend language with a wide array of examples
- A look at integrating the DSL approach into existing code bases
- Detailed discussions on how the DSL ensures performant execution of the generated code

The hands-on sessions guided the students through small numerical exercises, starting from simple differential operators up to a complete shallow water solver implemented in dusk.

The PsyClone lectures contained:

- A general overview of the PsyClone toolchain followed by an in-depth look at the whole PsyClone ecosystem
- Interoperability of the PsyClone and dusk and dawn toolchains
- How PsyClone could be applied to the existing models NEMO as well as LFRIC
- A look at the different optimisations (shared and distributed memory) performed by PsyClone

All lectures as well as hands-on sessions have been recorded and are available on the ESiWACE YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC4VnUf-ZZ0E200nK5M0GPmg>). The OER lecture is available at <https://www.oercommons.org/courseware/lesson/86681>.

4.3 C++ programming

C++ is a very powerful programming language, used worldwide to develop complex and performance-critical applications. It is thus an important candidate for developing HPC applications. Mastering the power of the language requires substantial effort but pays off as projects scale up in size and complexity. As the hardware architectures become more and more diverse and complex, C++ allows the implementation of the proper abstractions to make applications sustainable in the future. Specifically, C++ allows the development of type safe, flexible and portable functionalities, with no runtime overhead.

The C++ HPC course, and the resulting OER materials subsequently available at <https://www.oercommons.org/courseware/lesson/87057> had units derived largely from our experience using C++ for HPC. The course required a basic knowledge of C++ programming in order to put these advanced topics into a proper context. Several C++ use cases were provided as an illustration of how C++ could be used productively in the HPC setting. Finally, there was also a unit containing C++ exercises, which are publicly available in a repository.

The C++ course covered the following topics:

- Introduction
- Values and Object Initialisation
- Name Resolution

- Templates
- Move Semantics
- Constexpr / Consteval / Constinit, Lambdas and functions
- STL
- Ranges
- Resource Management
- Concept-based design
- Four use cases: DLAF, GROMACS, Tasking library, Kokkos
- Q&A / Exercises

The course itself was held on October 11-13, 2021, in a virtual format due to the covid-19 pandemic. 41 persons signed up for the course, and we saw a maximum of 28 participants at any given time. Due to our organisational guidelines, we were not allowed to ask for demographic information at registration time, so we opted for a voluntary survey. There were 27 responses in total. Regarding gender, 20 identified themselves as male, four as female, and three chose not to respond. A majority of the attendees came from the academic sector (23 participants with among them seven master or PhD students, four post-docs, 10 researchers or scientists) and four came from the industry. In spite of the lack of a physical presence, most participants found the course valuable in the course survey, with very few reporting that it was either too difficult or too easy.

4.4 Code coupling with OASIS3-MCT

OASIS3-MCT is a coupling library that can be used to exchange information between different codes modelling the different components of the Earth System, e.g. the ocean or the atmosphere. OASIS3-MCT, the latest version of the OASIS coupler, is fully parallel and is used by at least 67 modelling groups worldwide to assemble more than 80 different coupled applications.

In the framework of ESiWACE2, a Small Private Online Course (SPOC) on “Code Coupling with OASIS3-MCT” was set up. In this SPOC mixing theory, videos, quizzes and hands-on, participants learn how to use OASIS3-MCT. The goal in this course is to instrument two toy models in order to set up a coupled model exchanging coupling fields, and to learn about the regridding function in OASIS3-MCT. A 3-minute video with more details on this SPOC is available at <https://cerfacs.fr/en/online-training-sessions/>.

The different parts of the SPOC are:

- Introduction to the course
- Instrument your code with OASIS3-MCT API routines
- Create the OASIS3-MCT configuration file, namcouple
- Calculation of regridding weights and addresses in OASIS3-MCT
- Additional exercises
- Final Exam
- Final words and satisfaction survey

Three sessions were organised in 2020, 2021 and 2022, one per year.

1. **First SPOC session, July 6-10, 2020**

A first session was held on July 6-10, 2020 with 10 participants (7 males, 3 females): 6 from France (LEGOS), 3 from Vietnam (University of Science and Technology of Hanoi), 1 from the UK (MetOffice). This first version of the SPOC, which at the time did not include the section on the calculation of the regriding weights, required from the participants about 15 hours of work to be spent over the week.

Out of 10 participants, one abandoned the course quite early, and one assembled his coupled model with OASIS3-MCT himself without providing further feedback. Three other participants did not complete the SPOC even though we offered them the possibility of completing it afterwards. Therefore six people completed the SPOC on time and answered the satisfaction survey. This survey was at the time quite basic and we do not show all answers here. We could nevertheless conclude that the videos, graphics and chapter divisions were well adapted and provided satisfactory information. The participants made some mistakes when answering the quizzes, but this can be considered part of the learning process. However, the feedback indicated that the programming exercises might be too guided. Overall, the feedback received suggested that the training was a good start for using OASIS3-MCT in a real coupled model, but that the participants understood that the bulk of the work was still in front of them.

2. **Second SPOC session, April 29 - May 12, 2021**

A second session was organised from April 29th to May 12th, 2021. We had evaluated that the training would require 20 hours of work to be spent over these 2 weeks, as a whole section on regriding had been added compared to the first session. 11 people (4 females, 7 males) registered from different countries around the world: France: 2, Netherlands: 1, Italy: 1, UK: 1, Germany: 1, Spain: 1, Canada: 1, USA: 2, Taiwan: 1. Out of 11 registered attendees, nine completed the SPOC and two did not even start.

The grades obtained in the quizzes by the nine participants who completed the SPOC were 100% almost everywhere; the only exception was the section on the configuration file, where two persons obtained 82%, and the section on regriding, where four persons obtained 80% and one person 40%. In the final exam, seven of the nine participants achieved a grade of 82% or above, and two participants achieved 26%, as they had completed less than a third of the exam. Overall, we conclude that the SPOC globally succeeds in transferring the basic concepts needed to use OASIS3-MCT when participants attend the SPOC and complete all parts.

Appendix 1 shows the questions and answers of the different parts of the 2021 SPOC satisfaction survey. For the first section on global satisfaction and motivation, all participants answered "yes" or "rather yes", which is quite satisfactory. The second section was mainly about teaching aspects; for most questions, the majority of the participants were satisfied or highly satisfied, which is reassuring; however, one person was not so happy about the "Clarity of the teacher messages" and "Teacher capacity to account for participants reaction" answering "unsatisfactory" to those points. The question on "Participants involvement" got 25% of "unsatisfactory" and 75% of "satisfactory", which noted probably a deficit of interaction between the participants through the forum. The third section was about the educational material used in the SPOC. The answers indicate that on average the SPOC material (graphics, chapters, quizzes) was appropriate. However, the videos might contain too much information and the programming exercises might be too guided, which had been noted also in the 2020 session. Finally, in the fourth section on their global satisfaction about the SPOC, 38% and 62% of the participants answered "good" and "very good", respectively, which can be considered as very positive.

3. **Third SPOC session, March 21 - April 6, 2022**

The third and last SPOC session was held from March 21st to April 6th, over 2.5 weeks. The content of the SPOC was identical with the second session in 2021 and required 20 hours of work by the participants. 12 persons registered (10 males, 2 females). Out of the 12 registered attendees, 9 took and passed the final exam (one with 89%, and the other eight ones with 100%). One person followed

the entire SPOC but did not try the final exam, another person went through parts 1 to 4 of the SPOC with good results in the quizzes, but neither worked on the 5th part nor on the exam. Yet another person barely worked on the SPOC. Overall we conclude that the rate of attendance and success is quite good.

Depending on the sections, 5 or 6 attendees have answered the satisfaction survey, the results of which are presented in Appendix 2. As in the year 2021, all participants answered "yes" or "rather yes" for the first section on their global satisfaction and motivation, which is again quite satisfactory. It has to be noted that 50% of the participants answered that they took more time than the 20 hours announced, which is something we will take into account in the next announcement. For the second and third sections, the survey had been revised compared to 2021 so that grade 1 and grade 4 now always corresponds to a negative and positive answer respectively. For the second section on teaching aspects, we note that all points were rated "satisfactory" or "highly satisfactory" this year. Again, the interaction between the participants seems to be low. Regarding the educational material (third section), the feedback is rather positive with a slight damper on the videos, as in 2020 and 2021. But the overall satisfaction of the participants is globally quite high with 86% absolutely satisfied and 14% satisfied.

4.5 Visualisation and High Performance Data Analytics (HPDA)

As the volumes of weather and climate data expand, it becomes of paramount importance for scientists to exploit the proper techniques and solutions for efficient handling of massive amounts of data and knowledge extraction. The online training course on High Performance Data Analytics (HPDA) and Visualisation, organised by CMCC and DKRZ in the context of the ESiWACE2 project was aimed at increasing scientists' expertise on data analysis and visualisation applied to climate and weather domains, using open source tools such as Ophidia and ParaView. Three courses were planned to be held during the ESiWACE2 project lifetime, one per year in 2020, 2021 and 2022, respectively. The first two courses have already been completed at the time of writing this deliverable, and the last one is planned for September 6-9, 2022. The training covered topics from simple analytics tasks to workflows and applications (e.g., python-based), with the goal of providing some best practices and guidelines for dealing with processing massive scientific datasets and visualisation on HPC architectures. The three training courses have the same structure, each lasting 8 hours and divided into four 2-hour sessions, i.e., two sessions covering HPDA-related aspects, and the other two focusing on visualisation aspects. Specifically, the topics covered in the three training courses include:

- Introduction to big data, scientific data challenges, HPDA and analytics at scale
- Introduction to data visualisation workflows, from post to in-situ
- Interactive analysis with Jupyter Notebooks and data analytics workflows for eScience
- Overview of open-source solutions, such as Ophidia for HPDA and ParaView for visualisation
- Data analytics demo/examples with Ophidia and Python data science libraries
- Visualisation demo/examples with ParaView

The courses followed a very practical approach. Besides the more theoretical introductory lectures, a large part of the time was devoted to showing examples of real-world applications, walkthrough tutorials and demos, as well as providing practical hands-on sessions. In particular, the courses gave practical examples of real applications of Ophidia for data analytics and ParaView for visualisation in the climate and weather domain. The training targets an audience from diverse backgrounds, ranging from computer to Earth system scientists working in the field of weather and climate research, and at different career stages; from students, young scientists, up to more experienced researchers/engineers who wish to improve their data analytics and

ESiWACE2 HPDA and VIS Course 2021

📅 Sep 13, 2021, 2:30 PM → Sep 16, 2021, 4:30 PM Europe/Berlin

👤 Donatello Elia, Niklas Roeber (DKRZ), Florian Ziemer, Dela Spickermann (Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum GmbH)

Description

As the volumes of weather and climate data expand, it is of paramount importance for scientists to exploit techniques and solutions able to efficiently extract knowledge from these data.

This online training course aims to increase scientists' expertise on data analysis and visualization applied to climate and weather domains, using high-performance data analytics (HPDA) and visualization tools available from the open source market (i.e., Ophidia and ParaView).

Figure 2: Snapshot from the 2021 HPDA and Visualisation course web page

visualisation skills. The only requirements to be able to fully take advantage of the course contents are a basic understanding of Python, Linux, the NetCDF data format and general aspects concerning climate/weather data. Slides and training material (including scripts and examples) have been provided for the courses along with the video recording of the sessions. Moreover, as reported in D6.4, starting from the HPDA and visualisation course organised in 2021, a set of PDF slides and video lectures on HPDA has been prepared and submitted as OER material (<https://www.oercommons.org/courseware/lesson/86887>).

1. First HPDA and Visualisation training 2020

The first training ran over four weeks in October and beginning of November, covering two hours per session. The training combined presentations and hands-on sessions, scheduled as follows:

- Session 1: Introduction to Ophidia, 6th October 2020
- Session 2: Introduction to ParaView (mainly 2D), 13th October 2020
- Session 3: Ophidia advanced concepts, 22nd October 2020
- Session 4: Advanced ParaView use, 3rd November 2020

The sessions were recorded and made freely available on the ESiWACE YouTube channel after the training course (<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL6g8Tn4IGyTmeB7nmDVF15CkRwbdS4P04>).

Participants were given instructions on how to set up their environment with the required software and datasets before the start of the course. Links to video recordings, slides and training material are available on the training web page: <https://www.esiwace.eu/events/hpda-training-2020> .

The 2020 online training course had nearly 90 registrations from several European and non-European countries, including Germany, Italy, India, Sweden, Australia, UK, Australia, France, Hungary, Nigeria, Serbia, China, Mozambique, Turkey, Cyprus, Denmark, Egypt, Guinea, Mexico, Nepal, Taiwan and the US. Each training session was attended by 15 to 40 people, with an average of 20 participants per session. A story about the first training was also published on the ESiWACE web portal:

<https://www.esiwace.eu/the-project/stories/training-on-hpda-and-vis-2020> .

2. Second HPDA and Visualisation training 2021

The second HPDA and visualisation course was organised based on the experience of the first training course, providing a similar structure but with more time dedicated to practical hands-on sessions. Moreover, differently from the first course, the second one had a more compact format and was scheduled over a single week, from the 13th to the 16th of September, 2021, according to the following calendar:

- Session 1: Introduction to ParaView, 13th September 2021
- Session 2: Advanced ParaView use, 14th September 2021
- Session 3: Introduction to Ophidia, 15th September 2021
- Session 4: Ophidia advanced concepts, 16th September 2021

As with the first course in 2020, the sessions were recorded and made available on the ESiWACE YouTube channel after training had been completed

(<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL6g8Tn4IGyTm131hQQfYyn7tJIsWGxwft>). Also in this case, instructions were provided to participants on how to set up their hands-on environment with the required software and datasets before the start of the course. In particular, in order to support the attendees with running the HPDA hands-on parts, a Docker-based container was also prepared, containing all software and required tools (<https://hub.docker.com/r/ophidiabigdata/ophidia-training>). Additional information about the event and links to the material and video recordings is available at: <https://indico.dkrz.de/e/esiwace-hpda-vis-2021>. The 2021 course had 61 registrations (12 females, 48 males, 1 decided to not respond) from around 20 countries worldwide. The most represented countries were Germany, Italy, India, France, Ireland, and Spain. Registrations mainly came from academia or research centres, with more than 50% being early career scientists or students. Each training session was attended by between 13 to 33 persons, with an average of 20 participants per session.

Training participants were asked to fill out a survey after the training course. The results collected from the replies show a generally positive impact of the training. The course was considered useful by the majority of respondents, and most of them would recommend following this type of training to their colleagues. In particular, the hands-on parts of the sessions were well rated overall, although survey responses showed the need to have more time devoted to practical aspects . These considerations will be taken into account for similar events in the future and especially for the final course organised within ESiWACE2.

After completion of the event, the following news item was published on the ESiWACE web portal: <https://www.esiwace.eu/news/news/hpda-vis-training-2021-completed>.

3. Third HPDA and Visualisation training 2022

The event is scheduled for September 6-9, 2022 and will follow a similar format to the previous one held in 2021.

4.6 Containerisation

The reliance on computing resources by an increasing number of scientific disciplines is introducing new requirements and use cases in HPC environments. Scientific software stacks required for simulation or data analysis are becoming ever more rich and complex, combining custom and off-the-shelf code, with corresponding increases in build times, maintenance effort, and dependency management challenges. Modern scientific users also demand more interactive workflows, tailor-made execution environments and better integration with web and cloud technologies.

Such diversity is pushing software development and distribution towards lightweight virtualisation technologies like Linux application containers, upon which scientists rely more and more to run their experiments. Specifically, containers address many of the requirements needed by researchers in terms of isolated dependency stacks, portability, reproducibility, and ease of distribution. In this context, Docker is the de-facto standard as a platform for the creation and distribution of containers, supporting virtualised infrastructures, bare-metal infrastructures, GPU devices, I/O virtualisation, and orchestration. However, several design decisions make Docker unsuitable for HPC systems, a fact which led to the creation of HPC-focused container solutions, capable of blending the convenience of containers with the unique characteristics of HPC environments.

In the scope of the ESiWACE2 project, two lectures about containerisation applied to scientific computing were organised, with the following main objectives:

- teach the fundamental concepts of Linux containers and communicate the advantages of containers for scientific software workflows
- familiarise students with Docker, currently the most popular general-purpose container solution
- demonstrate how to deploy containers on high performance systems through an HPC-focused container tool.

The overall theme of the lectures was to outline an end-to-end scientific computing workflow utilising Docker containers, starting from a personal workstation and going all the way to a large-scale supercomputer. The lectures targeted students with no previous knowledge about containers and featured a mix of frontal presentations, live tutorials and self-paced hands-on exercises. Handout material was prepared to guide students through the hands-on exercises. Presentation slides, handout material and code samples were made available through a GitHub public repository under the ETHZ/CSCS organisation. An introductory video to the hands-on session was also recorded and made available to the students. Lectures were delivered as part of the ESiWACE Summer Schools on Effective HPC for Climate and Weather in 2020 and 2021, respectively.

After the summer schools, video recordings and materials from both lectures were selected, organised and published as OER material (<https://www.oercommons.org/courseware/lesson/86725>).

1. Containers lecture at the Summer School on Effective HPC for Climate and Weather in 2020

The lecture was held on Thursday, August 27th, 2020. The concepts of process isolation through Linux namespaces and the use of self-sufficient units of software called "images" were presented as the basics of containerisation. The advantages of container workflows in terms of portability, prescriptiveness, deployability, and testing were outlined and commented on. Docker was then introduced as a general-purpose container solution, explaining its basic workflow and image distribution model based on cloud registries. A live tutorial then showcased interactively how to use Docker commands to manage and run containers on personal computers, and how to build applications of increasing complexity into portable container images. Particular focus was given to packaging and using MPI libraries and the CUDA Toolkit within container images, since these software resources are key enablers of highly-efficient scientific applications.

The second part of the lecture presented the limitations of Docker when applied to high-end computing systems and introduced Sarus, an HPC-focused container engine capable of leveraging the performance

and scalability of supercomputers, while maintaining a consistent user experience with Docker. A second live tutorial demonstrated the basic actions and commands of Sarus by deploying the images created earlier during the lecture on the Piz Daint supercomputer at CSCS; the performance difference made possible by the full utilisation of HPC hardware was highlighted, as well as the integration possibilities with the workload manager and parallel file systems.

After the frontal presentations and tutorials, a hands-on session gave students the chance to freely experiment with building and running containers. A Docker installation was made available as part of the virtual machine image provided by the Summer School for self-paced lab sessions. A handout step-by-step guide was provided to replicate the examples from the Docker tutorial, reinforcing the knowledge acquired from the previous frontal teaching. The handout also included more advanced exercises and concepts, encouraging the students to explore additional topics. The exercises and instructions in the handout material were verified to execute correctly within the summer school virtual machine image.

2. Containers lecture at the Summer School on Effective HPC for Climate and Weather in 2021

The lecture was held on Thursday, August 26th, 2021. The first part of the lecture remained unchanged from the format proposed in 2020. This refers to the fundamentals of containerisation and the live tutorial to Docker. Due to the changes to time slots decided by the summer school organisers, the content about deploying containers on HPC environments was reduced to the limitations of Docker, an overview of the most established HPC-focused solutions, and a quick spotlight on the Sarus container engine. The hands-on session remained largely unchanged from 2020, featuring only minor updates to the handout material in order to improve clarity and include a few additional topics and exercises.

4.7 Summer Schools on Effective HPC for Climate and Weather

Two summer schools with presentations and hands-on sessions on all ESiWACE2 trainings but also including other topics were organised as a one-week event in August 2020 and 2021, respectively, and were held fully virtually due to covid-19 restrictions. We have presented a detailed report on those summer schools in deliverable D6.1 "Report on summer school and its material" (https://zenodo.org/record/5795447#.Yma_my8RpN0).

The scope of the schools was to train young researchers and software engineers in methods, tools, and theoretical knowledge to make effective use of HPC environments and generate insights. The sessions included about 34 hours of lectures and 18 hours of hands-on and lab practicals. The topics covered were:

- Extreme-Scale Computation
- Parallel Programming in Practice
- Modern Storage
- Input/Output and Middleware
- Machine Learning
- High Performance Data Analytics and Visualisation
- Performance Analysis
- Containers

Overall 289 people registered for the schools and 87 obtained a certificate of attendance as they had attended most of the sessions in the respective school. Video recordings of the sessions were published on YouTube after the event in order to allow even more attendees to enjoy the training. The post-event survey suggests that more than 95% of the attendees had at least a good experience and generally, a favorable appraisal

was given. In the CoE proposal, we had expected to host 30-40 students per school, and this was largely surpassed by the total number of attendees at the summer schools. We conclude that the lectures and lab practicals were generally well-received and, despite the schools being virtual events, we successfully delivered the planned training events.

4.8 Appendix 1 - SPOC 2021 Satisfaction Survey

SPOC 2021 Satisfaction survey – global satisfaction, understanding and motivation

	no	rather no	rather yes	yes
Is your usage need for OASIS3-MCT satisfied by this training?	0%	0%	13%	88%
Is your need for understanding and mastering OASIS3-MCT satisfied by this training?	0%	0%	25%	75%
Did your motivation positively evolve during the training?	0%	0%	25%	75%

SPOC 2021 Satisfaction survey – teaching aspects

EVALUATION (1 = HIGHLY UNSATISFACTORY AND 4 = HIGHLY SATISFACTORY) RÉSULTATS				
	1	2	3	4
Material	0%	0%	50%	50%
Duration	0%	0%	0%	100%
Quality of the teaching aids	0%	0%	25%	75%
Agreement between objectives set and reached	0%	0%	25%	75%
Clarity of the teachers messages	0%	13%	25%	63%
Balance between theory and examples	0%	0%	25%	75%
Teachers capacity to account for participants reactions	0%	13%	25%	63%
Benefit of the course from a personal point of view	0%	0%	38%	63%
Benefit of the course from a professional point of view	0%	0%	38%	63%
Participants involvement	0%	25%	75%	0%

SPOC 2021 Satisfaction survey – educational material

EVALUATION (1 = ABSOLUTELY RIGHT AND 4 = ABSOLUTELY FALSE) RÉSULTATS				
	1	2	3	4
The graphic choices (typography, figures) are coherent and helpful.	50%	13%	25%	13%
The division of the training into chapters are coherent and helpful.	63%	0%	0%	38%
The different video lengths are well adapted to my learning process.	63%	0%	13%	25%
The given information in the videos are precise.	50%	13%	0%	38%
Each video gives me a good understanding of the OASIS3-MCT part it covers.	50%	13%	13%	25%
Videos present too much information and therefore I found them difficult to follow.	38%	13%	13%	38%
I have often felt lost watching the videos.	25%	13%	25%	38%
The multiple choice quizzes allow me to check if I understood of the videos.	38%	38%	13%	13%
The feedback from the multiple choice quizzes helps me to clarify my understanding of the videos.	38%	38%	13%	13%
I've often made mistakes on multiple choice quizzes.	0%	38%	63%	0%
Practical programming exercises in the first part were too guided.	0%	75%	25%	0%
Practical programming exercises in the second part (namcouple) ere too guided.	0%	50%	50%	0%
I often got stuck during application exercises on atmos.F90 and ocean.F90.	25%	13%	13%	50%
In the first part, I had to download the solutions during the practical exercises.	25%	13%	0%	63%
In the second part (namcouple), I had to download the solutions during the practical exercises.	25%	13%	0%	63%
Now, I feel able to use OASIS3-MCT for my own needs.	25%	38%	13%	25%

SPOC 2021 Satisfaction survey – global satisfaction

GLOBAL SATISFACTION ABOUT THIS COURSE (1:VERY BAD, 5:VERY GOOD) RÉSULTATS					
	1	2	3	4	5
<p>Global satisfaction about this course :</p>	0%	0%	0%	38%	63%

4.9 Appendix 2 - SPOC 2022 Satisfaction Survey

SPOC 2022 Satisfaction survey – global satisfaction, understanding and motivation

	no	rather no	rather yes	yes	no answer
Is your usage need for OASIS3-MCT satisfied by this training?	0%	0%	33%	67%	0%
Is your need for understanding and mastering OASIS3-MCT satisfied by this training?	0%	0%	50%	50%	0%
Did your motivation positively evolve during the training?	0%	0%	33%	67%	0%
You have used more time than the 20 hours announced	17%	33%	0%	50%	0%
You have used less time than the 20 hours announced	50%	17%	17%	17%	0%

SPOC 2022 Satisfaction survey – teaching aspects (1=highly unsatisfactory, 4= highly satisfactory)

	1	2	3	4	no answer
Duration (i.e. over 2.5 weeks)	0%	0%	17%	83%	0%
Quality of teaching aids	0%	0%	17%	67%	17%
Agreement between objectives set and reached	0%	0%	17%	83%	0%
Clarity of the teachers' messages	0%	0%	33%	67%	0%
Balance between theory and examples	0%	0%	0%	100%	0%
Teachers capacity to account for participants' reactions	0%	0%	0%	67%	33%
Benefit of the course from a professional point of view	0%	0%	0%	100%	0%
Quality of exchanges between participants	0%	17%	0%	33%	50%

SPOC 2022 Satisfaction survey – educational material & global satisfaction (1 = absolutely false, 4 = absolutely right)

	1	2	3	4	no answer
The graphic choices (typography, figures) are coherent and helpful.	0%	0%	43%	57%	0%
The division of the training into chapters are coherent and helpful.	0%	0%	14%	86%	0%
The distinction between theory and practical work seems appropriate (alternation and duration dedicated to each part)	0%	0%	14%	86%	0%
The different video lengths are well adapted to my learning process.	0%	0%	14%	86%	0%
The given information in the videos is precise.	0%	14%	29%	57%	0%
Each video gives a good understanding of the OASIS3-MCT part it covers.	0%	14%	29%	57%	0%
Videos present just enough information and therefore I found them easy to follow.	0%	14%	0%	86%	0%
The multiple choice quizzes allowed me to check if I understood well the videos.	0%	0%	43%	57%	0%
The feedback from the multiple choice quizzes helped me to clarify my understanding of the videos.	0%	0%	14%	86%	0%
I have very seldom made mistakes on multiple choice quizzes	0%	14%	57%	29%	0%
Guidance of the programming exercises in the first part is adequate	0%	0%	14%	86%	0%
Guidance of the practical programming exercises in the second part (namcouple) is adequate.	0%	0%	29%	71%	0%
Application exercises on atmos.F90 and ocean.F90. went smoothly for me	0%	0%	57%	43%	0%
In the first part, I didn't have to download the solutions during the practical exercises, or only very seldom	0%	0%	29%	71%	0%
In the second part (namcouple), I didn't have to download the solutions during the practical exercises or only very seldom	0%	0%	71%	29%	0%
Now, I feel able to use OASIS3-MCT for my own needs.	0%	0%	43%	57%	0%
Your global satisfaction regarding this course ?	0%	0%	14%	86%	0%

5 References

No related reference

6 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

No particular difficulties were encountered when producing the training sessions organised through ESiWACE2, besides the fact that two trainings planned as face-to-face were finally delivered online because of covid-19. The virtual format allowed more people to attend the sessions, which is positive, although the advantages of face-to-face sessions remain unquestionable.

7 How this deliverable contributes to the European strategies for HPC

The trainings described here are essential, as running (pre-) exascale applications on the most advanced HPC platforms asks for well-trained and highly-qualified staff ensuring sound programming of the applications and expert use of all components in the ecosystem. These trainings result in a larger number (over 400) of scientists and engineers with higher qualifications in the use and optimisation of climate and weather applications on tier-0 machines, increasing HPC awareness in that community. Ultimately, these trainings will allow climate and weather research to be more productive, favouring European scientific excellence in that field.

8 Sustainability

The trainings offered constitute a first transfer of general knowledge from ESiWACE2 experts to the community while the services from WP3 constitute a precise and individual answer to user specific problems encountered with their code on the path to exascale. These trainings leverage the developments done in WP1 (for OASIS3-MCT), WP2 (DSL, Containerisation), WP4 (Input/Output) and WP5 (HPDA).

These trainings are coordinated at the EU level, through the supervision of the FOCUS CoE.

9 Dissemination, Engagement and Uptake of Results

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

X	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

We ensure the uptake by the targeted audience through the following actions:

- All training sessions are listed on the training page of the ESiWACE web site (see <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/trainings>)
- Each training session is announced with a specific news (see e.g. <https://www.esiwace.eu/events/spoc-oasis3-mct-2022>) and mails to different mailing lists in the community.

- The calendar of the trainings is published at <https://calendar.time.ly/5r0mgbac/stream> and on the new portal for European HPC services at <https://hpc-portal.eu/node/1414>, together with the trainings of the other CoEs, thanks to the coordination of the FOCUS CoE.

9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

The training themselves were or will be delivered as follows:

Past Trainings	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo or Web Link	Estimated number of persons reached
Lucas Benedicic et al. (ETHZ) session at "Container Hackathon for Modellers"	3-5/12/2019 - Lugano (CH)	Scientific Community	https://zenodo.org/record/4323261	15
Online course on Code Coupling using OASIS3-MCT	6-10/07/2020 (online)	Scientific Community	N/A	10
Summer School on Effective HPC for Climate and Weather	24-28/08/ 2020 (online)	Scientific Community	https://www.esiwace.eu/the-project/stories/summer-school	162
High Performance Data Analytics and Visualisation 2020	6,13,22/10 and 3/11/2020 (online)	Scientific Community	https://www.esiwace.eu/events/hpda-vis-2020	90
Domain Specific Languages (DSLs) for Weather and Climate	23-27/11/2020 (online)	Scientific Community	https://www.esiwace.eu/events/dsl-training	60
Online course on Code Coupling using OASIS3-MCT	29/05 - 12/06/2021 (online)	Scientific Community	N/A	11
Summer School on Effective HPC for Climate and Weather	23-27/08/2021 (online)	Scientific Community	https://hps.vi4io.org/events/2021/esiwace-school	125
High Performance Data Analytics and Visualisation 2021	13-16/09/2021 (online)	Scientific Community	https://www.esiwace.eu/events/hpda-vis-2021	60
Advanced C++ online course organised by CSCS/ETHZ	11-13/10/2021 (online)	Scientific Community	https://www.esiwace.eu/events/c-workshop	35
Online course on Code Coupling using OASIS3-MCT	21/05-06/04/2022 (online)	Scientific Community	N/A	12

(1)

Planned Trainings	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo or Web Link	Estimated number of persons reached
High Performance Data Analytics and Visualisation 2022	6-9/09/2022 (online)	Scientific Community	N/A	planned

9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

N/A

9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

N/A